

Comparison of the Opinions of High School Students, Teachers, Parents and Pedagogue Students on Ideal Teacher Interaction

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Abstract

Based on Leary's interpersonal model (Interpersonal Circumplex), Wubbels elaborated the scheme of interpersonal behaviour that was completed by questionnaires (Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction (QTI)). In this study, we compare the results of our previous research regarding the ideal teacher interaction. We would like to highlight the significant differences between the opinions of parents, teachers, high school students, and pedagogue students. Teacher interaction in the classroom is extremely important because quality teacher-student classroom interaction is crucial in promoting student learning, and research using the QTI measurement tool in the classroom environment has contributed significantly to the understanding of the complex interactions of teaching.

Keywords: *comparison, ideal teacher interaction, high school students, teachers, parents, pedagogue students.*

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Introduction

Research results show that the perception of the ideal teacher is grouped along two aspects. One aspect emphasizes the teacher's personal qualities (Korthagen, 2004); while the other evaluates the ideal teacher along the knowledge of the subject taught, i.e., didactic and methodological knowledge (Arnon & Reichel, 2007). Between the two main aspects is the approach that concerns the ideal teacher's ability to engage in meaningful dialogue with students (Semenova & Khanolainen, 2024), which is manifested in teacher-student interaction. As a result of continuous technological development, geopolitical changes, mass migration and various global and local changes, the field of education is also undergoing a significant transformation (Hadar et al., 2020), in which the involvement of students in school processes (Khanolainen et al., 2023) and the expression of students' opinions are emphasized.

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Theoretical Background

Understanding students' perceptions of ideal teacher interactions is important in many ways and can directly contribute to improving the quality of teaching. Student feedback can help teachers understand what types of interactions and teaching methods students prefer. This knowledge can help teachers more effectively choose instructional strategies that better suit students' needs and learning styles. When teachers consider students' perceptions and accommodate their preferences, this can stimulate students' intrinsic motivation, which can be linked to attitudes toward the subject and the teacher (Fisher et al., 1995; Fisher & Rickard, 1998).

Darrell Fisher et al. (1995) developed three measuring tools based on Wubbels, one for the evaluation of a teacher by students, another for the self-evaluation of the teacher, and a third for determining the interpersonal behaviour that the teacher considers ideal. In our current research, we used this third tool, and we asked students, teachers, and parents about their opinions about the teachers' ideal interpersonal behaviour.

Wubbels defined ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour in 8 octants. The interpretation of Wubbels' octanes can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of Behaviour Categories Defined by Leary and Wubbels

The categories in the Wubbels model	Detailed description
Leadership Behaviour (LEA)	notice what is happening; lead, organise, give orders; set tasks, propose solutions, explain, arouse the students' interest
Helpful/Friendly Behaviour (HFR)	assist, show interest in students' problems, involved, behave friendly and politely, have a sense of humour
Understanding Behaviour (UND)	listen with interest, empathic behaviour, show confidence and understanding, initiate conflict resolution, be patient, open
Student Responsibility and Freedom Behaviour (SRE)	provide opportunity for independent work; wait for class to let off steam; give freedom and responsibility; take into consideration the proposals of the students
Uncertain Behaviour (UNC)	no intervention to happening, stay in the background, apologise, wait and see how the wind blows, admit one is in the wrong
Dissatisfied Behaviour (DIS)	wait for silence, consider pros and cons, keep quiet, express dissatisfaction, eyes are angry, always ask questions, criticize
Admonishing Behaviour (ADM)	get angry, short-tempered, forbid, warn for mistakes, punish
Strict Behaviour (STR)	control of students, strict exams, strict evaluation, getting class silent, maintaining silence, setting rules and norms, exercising rules

Source: Tóth & Horváth, 2022: 76

Wubbels et al. (1985) found that teachers' behaviour is characterized by two aspects: didactic-pedagogical and relational. The didactic-pedagogical aspect is manifested in the choice of teaching methods and their appropriate application. The relational aspect helps in creating and achieving appropriate learning conditions and results. The relationship between teacher and student is considered crucial because it influences the development of the cognitive and, above all, affective side of the student's personality.

The didactic-pedagogical aspect is an expression of the teacher's professionalism and expertise, while the relational aspect is an expression of the teacher's personality.

Usually, one aspect is more prominent than the other in the manifestation of the teacher's behaviour towards students, but neither is independent of the other. After all, the teaching methods chosen by the teacher have an impact on the relationship between him/her and the students, the quality of which he/she can influence.

As Wubbels explains, the model of interpersonal teacher behaviour can present the teacher's general behavioural orientation through individual interpersonal terms, so that they can be used by students to judge how the teacher behaves in the classroom (Mainhard, 2015; Sun et al., 2018).

Comparison of the Results of the Researches

In this study, we compare the results obtained in previous research. We investigated the ideal teacher classroom interaction in three different samples: (1) among high school students (Szabó L. & Horváth, 2024a); (2) among teachers (Szabó L., 2025); and (3) among parents (Szabó L. & Horváth, 2024b). In all three studies, we worked with the Hungarian version of the QTI questionnaire created by Tóth & Horváth (2019). In the comparison of the results, we also include the research by Tóth & Horváth (2022), which (4) examined the opinions of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin on ideal teacher interaction (Tóth & Horváth, 2022). The comparison is conducted along the individual octants.

The admonishing (ADM) attitude covers interpersonal behaviours such as the teacher often being angry or irritable; liking to prohibit certain things and activities; often or always warning his students about their mistakes; often scolding and even punishing his students.

During the comparison, we work with an F-test. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the admonishing attitude can be found in Table 2, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Dissatisfied Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	10,75	4,023	16,18
Teachers	237	8,66	3,274	10,72
Parents	431	8,11	2,045	4,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	9,54	2,898	8,40

Source: own editing

Table 3. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Dissatisfied Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F _{emp} , F _{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	1,51; 1,34	3,87; 1,31	1,93; 1,33

Teachers		----	2,56, 1,29	1,28; 1,37
Parents			---	2,01; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 3 shows the significant differences we found in the admonishing attitude between the samples. According to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is much more characterized by the admonishing attitude than according to the teachers, parents, and Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin. According to teachers, the ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is much more characterized by the admonishing attitude than according to parents. According to the pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin the ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by the admonishing attitude more than the opinions of parents. In one case, we did not find a significant difference: in the case of the pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin and the teachers, which may be due to the fact that pedagogue students become teachers within a few years, so their opinions may be more similar.

The dissatisfied attitude covers interpersonal behaviours such as the teacher waiting for the class to quiet down; considering, demanding calm; having no problem expressing his/her dissatisfaction; often having an angry, grumpy look; always asking questions; and often criticizing his/her students. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the dissatisfied attitude can be found in Table 4, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 5.

Table 4. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Dissatisfied Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	10,2	4,72	22,28
Teachers	237	8,14	2,11	4,45
Parents	431	9,72	3,302	10,90
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	9,72	3,144	9,88

Source: own editing

Table 5. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Dissatisfied Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F _{emp} , F _{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	5,01; 1,34	2,04; 1,31	2,26; 1,33
Teachers		----	2,45, 1,29	2,22; 1,37
Parents			---	1,10; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 5 shows the significant differences we found in terms of dissatisfied attitudes between the samples:

- according to high school students, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a dissatisfied attitude much more than according to teachers
- according to high school students, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a dissatisfied attitude much more than according to parents
- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a dissatisfied attitude much more than according to the opinion of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to parents, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a dissatisfied attitude much more than according to teachers
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a dissatisfied attitude much more than the teachers' perception.

In one case, we found no significant difference: the opinions of parents and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin are the same regarding the dissatisfied attitude of the ideal teacher.

A helpful, friendly attitude covers interpersonal behaviours such as the teacher helping his/her students; showing interest in the students' problems; behaving in a friendly and polite manner with his/her surroundings; and having a sense of humour. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the helpful, friendly attitude can be found in Table 6, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 7.

Table 6. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Helpful, Friendly Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	26,38	4,732	22,39
Teachers	237	27,7	2,967	8,80
Parents	431	26,23	4,414	19,48
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	26,76	2,67	7,13

Source: own editing

Table 7. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Helpful, Friendly Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F _{emp} ; F _{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	2,54; 1,34	1,15; 1,31	3,14; 1,33
Teachers		----	2,14; 1,29	1,23; 1,37
Parents			---	2,73; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 7 shows the significant differences we found in terms of helpful, friendly attitudes between the samples:

- according to teachers, the ideal interpersonal behaviour of a teacher is characterized by a helpful, friendly attitude much more than according to the opinion of high school students
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a helpful, friendly attitude much more than according to the opinion of high school students
- according to teachers, the ideal interpersonal behaviour of a teacher is characterized by a helpful, friendly attitude much more than according to parents
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal interpersonal behaviour of a teacher is characterized by a helpful, friendly attitude much more than according to parents (Szabó, & Horváth, 2024)

In two cases, we found no significant differences: (1) the opinion of high school students is the same as that of parents regarding helpful, friendly teacher attitudes; and (2) the opinions of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin and teachers are the same regarding helpful, friendly teacher attitudes.

The leadership attitude covers interpersonal behaviours in which the teacher warns students about what is going to happen; leads and directs classroom activities; organizes; instructs; assigns tasks to students; suggests solutions; explains; and attracts students' attention. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the leadership attitude can be found in Table 8, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 9.

Table 8. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Leadership Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	25,77	3,128	9,78
Teachers	237	28,09	2,01	4,04
Parents	431	26,68	3,791	14,37
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	27	2,484	6,17

Source: own editing

Table 9. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Leadership Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F _{emp} ; F _{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	2,42; 1,34	1,46; 1,31	1,59; 1,33
Teachers		----	3,55; 1,29	1,53; 1,37
Parents			---	2,33; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 9 shows the significant differences we found in terms of leadership attitudes between the samples:

- according to teachers, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to high school students
- according to parents, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to high school students
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to the high school students
- according to teachers, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to parents
- according to teachers, ideal teacher interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a leadership attitude much more than according to parents (Szabó L., 2025)

A student responsibility and freedom attitude encompass interpersonal behaviours in which the teacher gives space for independent work; waits until the class is quiet; gives students freedom along with taking responsibility; and always takes students' suggestions into account. The means, standard deviations, and the squares (Anderson, & Bourke, 2000) of the standard deviation of the student responsibility and freedom attitude can be found in Table 10, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 11.

Table 10. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Student Responsibility and Freedom Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	18,98	4,11	16,89
Teachers	237	17,28	4,769	22,74
Parents	431	19,05	4,277	18,29
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	16,62	3,318	11,01

Source: own editing

Table 11. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Student Responsibility and Freedom Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F_{emp} , F_{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	1,35; 1,34	1,08; 1,31	1,53; 1,33
Teachers		----	1,24; 1,29	2,06; 1,37
Parents			---	1,66; 1,18

Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---
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Source: own editing

Table 11 shows the significant differences we found in terms of student responsibility and freedom attitudes between the samples:

- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a student responsibility and freedom attitude much more than according to teachers
- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a student responsibility and freedom attitude much more than according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to the teachers, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a student responsibility and freedom attitude than according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to parents, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a student responsibility and freedom attitude than according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin (Szabó L., & Horváth, 2024b).

In two cases, we found no significant differences: (1) the opinions of high school students are the same as the opinions of parents regarding the student responsibility and freedom attitude of the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour; and (2) the opinions of parents and teachers are the same regarding the student responsibility and freedom attitude of the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour.

A strict attitude covers interpersonal behaviours such as the teacher regularly checking students, strictly testing and evaluating them; requiring silence in class; frequently disciplining the class; and always requiring compliance with rules and regulations. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the strict attitude can be found in Table 12, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 13.

Table 12. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Strict Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	15,06	4,883	23,84
Teachers	237	14,9	5,338	28,49
Parents	431	15,74	4,257	18,12
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	16,56	3,978	15,82

Source: own editing

Table 13. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Strict Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F_{emp} , F_{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	1,19; 1,34	1,32; 1,31	1,51; 1,33
Teachers		----	1,57; 1,29	1,80; 1,37
Parents			---	1,15; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 13 shows the significant differences we found in terms of the strict attitudes between the samples:

- according to parents, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a strict attitude much more than according to high school students
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a strict attitude much more than according to high school students
- according to parents, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a strict attitude much more than according to teachers
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by a strict attitude much more than according to parents (Szabó L., 2025)

In two cases, we found no significant differences: (1) the opinion of high school students is the same as the opinion of teachers regarding the strict attitude; and (2) the opinions of parents and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin are also the same regarding the strict attitudes.

The uncertain attitude covers interpersonal forms of behaviour in which the teacher does not interfere in the course of things regarding the students; if necessary, he/she retreats into the background; if necessary, he/she apologizes; he/she waits to see how things will turn out; and he/she admits if the fault lies with him/her. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the uncertain attitude can be found in Table 14, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 15.

Table 14. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Uncertain Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	10,53	4,48	20,07
Teachers	237	7,18	2,38	5,66
Parents	431	8,26	2,093	4,38
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	8,16	2,994	8,96

Source: own editing

Table 15. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Uncertain Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F_{emp} , F_{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	3,55; 1,34	4,58; 1,31	2,24; 1,33
Teachers		----	1,29; 1,29	1,58; 1,37
Parents			---	2,04; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 15 shows the significant differences we found in terms of the uncertain attitudes between the samples:

- according to the opinion of high school students, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of teachers
- according to the opinion of high school students, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of parents
- according to the opinion of high school students, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to the opinion of parents, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of teachers
- than according to the opinion of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of teachers
- according to the opinion of the parents, the ideal teachers' interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an uncertain attitude much more than according to the opinion of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin

An understanding, consensus-seeking attitude encompasses interpersonal behaviours in which the teacher listens attentively to students; acts empathetically with students; radiates trust and understanding; is tolerant; encourages conflict resolution; is patient with students; and is open to new ideas and solutions. The means, standard deviations, and the squares of the standard deviation of the understanding attitude can be found in Table 16, while the empirical and critical values of the F-test are presented in Table 17.

Table 16. The Means, Standard Deviations, and the Squares of the Standard Deviation of the Understanding Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample	Sample size (persons)	The mean of the sample	The standard deviation of the sample	The squared standard deviation of the sample
High school students	326	26,98	3,412	11,64
Teachers	237	26,49	2,793	7,80

Parents	431	25,6	4,493	20,19
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin	336	26,7	2,634	6,94

Source: own editing

Table 17. Empirical and Critical Values of the F-Test of the Understanding Attitude in the Four Samples

Sample (F_{emp} , F_{crit})	High school students	Teachers	Parents	Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
High school students	---	1,49; 1,34	1,73; 1,31	1,68; 1,33
Teachers		----	2,59; 1,29	1,12; 1,37
Parents			---	2,91; 1,18
Pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin				---

Source: own editing

Table 17 shows the significant differences we found in terms of the understanding attitudes between the samples:

- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude much more than according to teachers
- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude much more than according to parents
- according to high school students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude much more than according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin
- according to teachers, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude much more than according to parents
- according to pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is characterized by an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude much more than according to parents (Szabó L., 2025)
- In one case, we found no significant difference: the opinions of teachers and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin are the same regarding the understanding, consensus-seeking teaching attitude (Szabó L., 2025).

Conclusion

We summarized the results of the four studies, identifying similarities and differences in the opinions of students, teachers, parents, and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin on ideal teacher interaction.

In the case of the admonishing attitude, we found a significant difference between the opinion of high school students and teachers (Bau, Hermila, & Latief, 2025). According to students, the ideal teacher's interpersonal behaviour is better characterized by the reprimanding and warning attitude than according to teachers and

parents (Szabó L., 2025). The opinions of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin are also similar, but we did not find a significant difference between the opinions of teachers and the pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin.

Regarding the dissatisfied attitude, high school students identify this attitude with the ideal teacher behaviour to the greatest extent, compared to the opinions of teachers and parents. The differences observed between parents and teachers also indicate that teachers and parents evaluate this attitude differently. As an exception, it can be mentioned that the opinions of parents and teacher students did not differ significantly in this regard.

In the case of helpful, friendly attitude, according to teachers and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher behaviour is characterized more by a helpful, friendly attitude than according to the opinion of high school students. Interestingly, the opinion of high school students regarding helpfulness is the same as the opinion of parents, while the opinion of teachers and pedagogue students is also similar.

Regarding the leadership attitude, teachers, parents, and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin all consider the controlling, assertive attitude to be the characteristic of the ideal teacher more than high school students. This attitude also showed significant differences between teachers and parents compared to the assessment of high school students.

In the case of student responsibility and freedom attitude, high school students consider this attitude to be much more important in case of the ideal teacher than teachers. Parents' opinions also differ from the opinions of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, but high school students' opinions are consistent with the opinions of the parents.

Regarding the strict attitude, according to the opinion of parents and pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin, the ideal teacher behaviour is characterized more by a strict attitude than according to the opinion of high school students. The opinions of teachers also differ from the opinions of high school students, however, there are also cases where the opinions of high school students are the same as the opinions of teachers (Dyatlov, Kovalev, & Chilingarova, 2023).

In the case of the uncertain attitude, according to high school students, this attitude characterizes the ideal teacher behaviour more strongly than according to the opinions of teachers and parents. The opinions of pedagogue students in the Carpathian Basin are also similar, and parents also show significant differences compared to their opinions.

In the case of the understanding, consensus-seeking attitude, according to the opinion of high school students, this attitude characterizes the ideal teacher behaviour much more than according to the opinion of other groups (teachers, parents, pedagogue student). The only case where we did not find a significant difference was the opinion of teachers and pedagogue student, which agreed on this regard. From this we can conclude that high school students see the behaviour of the ideal teacher from a different perspective than other groups, while the opinions of teachers and pedagogue student are close to each other in terms of an understanding, consensus-seeking attitude.

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